

Full Length Article

Governing high-integrity markets for ecosystem services

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ABSTRACT

There is growing global interest in the potential for ecosystem markets to facilitate climate and nature recovery. Yet, poorly designed and operated markets are prone to corporate “greenwashing” and negative consequences for nature and local communities. With the rapid scaling of ecosystem markets around the world, there is a need to systematically analyse ecosystem market governance principles, and identify the practical steps needed to implement these principles at national scales across multiple high-integrity ecosystem markets. The majority of principles published to date are designed to be applied at international scales or within single markets. However, national policy oversight is essential to ensure emerging ecosystem markets deliver natural capital outcomes and wider public benefits appropriate to the jurisdictions in which they operate.

This paper therefore analyses principles for the development and operation of high-integrity ecosystem markets, proposing how these could be operationalised in the UK, where governments are actively developing new governance regimes for rapidly proliferating voluntary markets and emission reduction or removal activities that occur within a company’s supply chain (“insetting”). The paper:

1. Provides the first comprehensive overview of compliance and voluntary carbon and other ecosystem markets operating in the UK in 2025, with a focus on new and emerging voluntary markets, alongside the first analysis of relevant ecosystem market actors in the UK.
2. Conducts a comparative analysis of existing national and international principles, identifying 15 high-level principles for governance, measurement, reporting and verification, and delivering wider benefits of high-integrity ecosystem markets, that could be applied by relevant market actors to the range of ecosystem markets identified in the UK as well as to insetting activities; and.
3. Proposes how these principles could be applied in an ecosystem markets governance hierarchy, showing policy, governance and market mechanisms and infrastructure that are being developed to implement the proposed principles in the UK, and discusses implications for international policy and markets.

The principles focus on robust governance, transparent measurement and verification, and equitable environmental and social benefits, ensuring credible and lasting outcomes from ecosystem markets. Taken together, the proposed market principles and governance hierarchy could be used to ensure the development of high-integrity ecosystem markets across the UK and internationally, helping national governments to responsibly build and scale these markets, and market actors design codes, schemes and projects that achieve additional carbon, biodiversity, and community gains across multiple contexts.

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1. Introduction

Climate change and the degradation of global ecosystems are taking us to the brink of ecosystem collapse (Rockström et al., 2009; Steffen et al., 2015; Nash et al., 2017). The increasingly dangerous impacts of these changes for humans and nature disproportionately affect those who have contributed least to climate change (IPCC, 2023). Keeping global warming within 1.5 °C of pre-industrial levels (Article 2, Paris Agreement, 2015; IPCC, 2018) requires social, economic and technological transformations on an unprecedented scale. More than half of global GDP is highly dependent on nature, according to the World Economic Forum (WEF, 2020). However, at COP15 of the UN Convention on Biological Diversity, 195 nations agreed that our world must not only become net zero, but also nature-positive (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2022). There is no pathway to limit global warming to 1.5 °C to halt devastating effects of climate change on people and planet, without addressing the loss of nature.

In addition to the well-recognised threats to human life, climate change, pollution and habitat loss pose major risks to businesses (IPCC, 2022). These include physical risks to infrastructure and supply chains (including stranded assets and impacts on the availability and quality of agricultural commodities), risks of non-compliance with new regulatory regimes to mitigate climate change, manage pollution and protect biodiversity, and reputational and market risks as customers increasingly demand action on nature and climate. To address these threats, businesses are increasingly integrating climate change, pollution and nature loss considerations into their risk management strategies, adopting more sustainable practices, and engaging in Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) reporting to enhance transparency and accountability (KPMG, 2024).

In addition to reducing impacts on the environment, businesses may seek to offset any residual impacts that cannot be avoided or removed from their operations and supply chains. Where companies focus on directly reducing their own greenhouse gas emissions—commonly referred to as Scope 1 (on-site emissions), Scope 2 (indirect emissions from purchased electricity, heat or steam) and Scope 3 (all other indirect emissions across the value chain) (GHG Protocol, 2023, forthcoming); this is often called *insetting*. In contrast to *insetting*, in *offsetting*, emissions are reduced or carbon sequestered and stored outside the company's supply chain. Offset markets facilitate private investment in natural capital through the generation of units that can be bought and sold voluntarily (voluntary markets) or to comply with regulation (compliance markets), for example, around offsetting the biodiversity impacts of development or emissions trading schemes that require companies in certain sectors to cap total greenhouse gas emissions, allowing them to buy and sell emission allowances to meet regulatory limits. Both *insetting* and *offsetting* enables businesses to invest with farmers and other landowners to enhance the ability of habitats to provide carbon, biodiversity uplift, clean water and other benefits, sometimes also reducing risks from climate change for vulnerable communities (referred to collectively in this paper as ecosystem markets) (Reed et al., 2022).

However, there are growing concerns in both *inset* and *offset* markets around the integrity of demand (ensuring that buyers' claims are accurate, transparently verified, and aligned with genuine reductions or improvements) and supply (outcomes are genuinely additional, accurately measured, fully transparent, and uphold environmental and social standards). Issues of carbon market integrity feature strongly in the Paris Agreement (Schneider and La Hoz Theuer, 2019) and subsequent negotiations (Cadman and Hales, 2022), and the UK's Committee on Climate Change (Committee on Climate Change, 2022) recommending that any expansion of carbon markets into new land uses and habitats should be limited until carbon credit integrity and the integrity of claims can be ensured. Critiques have tended to focus on carbon markets, but often apply more widely across other types of ecosystem market (Quatrini, 2021; Reed et al., 2022; Committee on Climate Change,

2022). These include:

- The concern that companies will use low-integrity ecosystem market units to make unsubstantiated claims to green credentials or achievement such as achieving 'net zero';
- Selling of units that are not robustly verified and so may not represent real climate or other benefits from nature; double-counting and selling of units or the sale of units from projects that would have happened anyway, and so are not additional;
- Challenges securing or demonstrating the permanence of nature-based solutions, which if reversed may not be reported or compensated for;
- Allowing companies to invest in offsets without first avoiding and minimizing impacts, for example, without first cutting their avoidable emissions or having long-term net zero commitments consistent with limiting global temperature increases to 1.5 degrees Celsius above pre-industrial levels;
- Concerns that projects that focus on single outcomes, such as carbon, may have negative unintended outcomes for other ecosystem services or local communities, for example in some cases leading to their displacement;
- Concerns that the existence of partial or narrowly focused schemes may give a misleading impression of sustainability, as they may fail to address the full spectrum of environmental and social impacts, allowing claims to be made while continuing harmful practices outside a scheme's limited scope; and

These are now being implemented on a voluntary basis by a number of international voluntary market players, but it is not clear how national governments should apply these principles within domestic offset markets or to *insetting*. Although there has been some attempt to analyse approaches to sustainable investment and finance in Europe (Quatrini and Costanza, 2023), there has been no systematic analysis of ecosystem market governance principles that have been proposed internationally, nor has there been any consideration of the wider policy and governance needed to implement these principles at a national scale. This is important, because without national policy oversight, international voluntary initiatives alone are unlikely to prevent the operation of low-integrity schemes, or ensure these markets deliver wider public benefits appropriate to the jurisdictions in which they operate.

This paper therefore seeks to identify principles for high-integrity ecosystem markets that could be operationalised at national scales across both *offsetting* and *insetting* activities. We discuss how these principles could be used to govern ecosystem markets in one national setting, the UK, to identify lessons for other nations seeking to responsibly scale ecosystem markets. In doing so, we seek to answer the following questions:

- How can clear governance frameworks be created to ensure additionality, permanence and transparency in emerging markets for ecosystem services?
- Which mechanisms can best address the risk of greenwashing and corporate overreliance on *offsetting* while promoting genuine emissions reductions and habitat restoration?
- How can relevant groups and local communities be meaningfully involved to enhance fairness and guard against unintended harms from private investment in natural capital and ecosystem services?
- Which tools and standards for measuring and verifying carbon, biodiversity and other benefits are most effective for maintaining confidence in these markets at scale?
- Which national-level policy interventions are most likely to encourage private investment in nature while securing long-term gains for society and the environment?

UK domestic ecosystem markets have proliferated rapidly, since the

introduction of government supported voluntary carbon markets for woodland creation (the Woodland Carbon Code in 2011 by the Forestry Commission, now owned and operated by Scottish Forestry) and peatland restoration (the Peatland Code in 2015 by the International Union for the Conservation of Nature's UK Peatland Programme). There are now multiple voluntary markets competing for woodland and peatland carbon, and emerging voluntary markets for other forms of carbon (e.g., arable and grassland soils, agroforestry, saltmarsh and biochar), biodiversity (e.g., [CreditNature, 2023](#)) and water quality (also referred to as nutrient trading e.g., Wessex Water's EnTrade platform; [EnTrade, 2023](#)). These are operating alongside compliance markets for carbon (e.g., the UK Emissions Trading Scheme) and biodiversity (Biodiversity Net Gain in England) and emission reduction or removal activities that occur within a company's supply chain, often described as insetting. In response to these developments, Scottish Government published Interim Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital Markets ([Scottish Government, 2022a](#)), leading to a Natural Capital Market Framework ([Scottish Government, 2024](#)), and Defra published a nature markets policy framework ([Defra, 2023](#)), which initiated work with the British Standards Institute (BSI) to create a set of independent standards against which codes and schemes can be evaluated.¹ Both of these UK government initiatives contain market governance principles, but neither go as far as many of the international initiatives upon which they build (ecosystem market policy is still under development in Wales and Northern Ireland). Drawing on this context, to develop nationally applicable governance principles for ecosystem markets, the paper:

1. Provides the first comprehensive overview of compliance and voluntary carbon and other ecosystem markets operating in the UK in 2025, with a focus on new and emerging voluntary markets, alongside the first analysis of relevant ecosystem market actors in the UK;
2. Conducts a comparative analysis of existing national and international market principles, identifying 15 high-level principles for governance, measurement, reporting and verification (MRV), and delivering wider benefits of high-integrity ecosystem markets, that could be applied by relevant market actors to the range of ecosystem markets identified in the UK; and
3. Proposes how these principles could be applied in an ecosystem market governance hierarchy, discussing policy, governance and market mechanisms and infrastructure that are being developed to implement the proposed principles in the UK, and implications for international policy and markets.

2. Methods

Research was conducted over a two-year period from 2021 to 2023 to evaluate ecosystem markets policy development across the UK, using a mixed methods approach that combined comparative analysis of ecosystem market documentation and a professionally facilitated workshop to collect primary data on market actors ([Fig. 1](#)). The research started with a narrative review of ecosystem markets currently operating in the UK, to provide an overview of the market context, prior to identifying and analysing relevant market actors. This context is then

¹ We refer to a code as a mechanism for issuing a unit from a project funded by an ecosystem market, including requirements for how projects are to be delivered and methodologies for quantifying ecosystem services. Codes can govern both voluntary markets (e.g., Plan Vivo's PV Nature) and compliance markets (e.g., Defra's Biodiversity Net Gain). Codes are often also referred to as schemes in the wider literature. We reserve the term standard for quality assurance standards that contain principles, guidance and/or requirements that codes must adhere to, if they wish to be accredited to the standard (e.g., ISO standards for verification bodies and BSI standards being developed for nature markets in the UK).

used to discuss a comparative analysis of international and national market principles, and how they could be applied to develop high-integrity ecosystem markets in the UK and similar countries.

2.1. Identifying UK ecosystem markets

A review was conducted to identify literature on ecosystem markets in the UK. For the purposes of this review, ecosystem markets were defined after [Muradian et al. \(2010\)](#) and [Wunder \(2015\)](#) as codes or schemes where ecosystem services are bought and sold in voluntary transactions, providing assurance of the delivery of services, creating incentives to align individual and/or collective land use decisions with social interests in the management of natural resources. Following this definition, ecosystem markets do not include nature investments or trades made for corporate social responsibility, or impact investment, where the transaction does not involve receiving specific, measurable and/or tradeable/retireable nature units (e.g., carbon credits) in return for investment.

Peer-reviewed literature on UK ecosystem markets was sought via the following searches, performed via Google Scholar, sorting for relevance: "ecosystem market*" AND UK; "nature market*" AND UK; "natural capital market*" AND UK; "payment* for ecosystem services" AND UK; "carbon market*" AND UK; and "biodiversity market*" AND UK. However, other than our former work on UK ecosystem markets ([Reed et al., 2022](#)), there were no other peer-reviewed papers about voluntary carbon, biodiversity or other ecosystem markets operating in the UK. Instead, papers tended to be general or global in scope and did not contain information specific to UK ecosystem markets (e.g. [Kroeger and Casey, 2007](#); [Teytelboym, 2019](#)), about privatisation of ecosystem services rather than ecosystem markets (e.g. [Bakker, 2005](#)), or about pilot programmes and feasibility studies rather than operational markets (e.g. [Ferreira, 2017](#); [van den Burg et al., 2022](#)). The exception was peer-reviewed literature on the compliance market for Biodiversity Net Gain in England; this literature was included in the review.

A narrative review of grey literature was conducted to identify compliance and voluntary carbon markets, and other compliance and voluntary ecosystem markets currently operating or in development in the UK. Narrative reviews typically rely on iterative searching and expert judgement to select, interpret and critique a diverse range of sources, enabling an integrated synthesis of both grey and peer-reviewed literature ([Petticrew et al., 2013](#); [Greenhalgh et al., 2018](#)). Narrative reviews are better suited than systematic reviews for topics or questions where it is not possible to identify specific interventions or outcomes ([Greenhalgh et al. 2018](#)).

Grey literature and literature from Google Scholar searches were supplemented with literature from projects funded in two investment readiness schemes by the English (the Environment Agency's Natural Environment Investment Readiness Fund) and Scottish Governments (NatureScot's Investment Ready Nature Scotland fund), as these were designed to stimulate the development of new markets across the UK. A "snowball sampling" method was then used to identify missing markets from investment readiness project teams and relevant policy teams in Scotland and England, until no new markets were found. Despite reaching this saturation point, it is however possible that some markets may have been missed.

2.2. Analysis of UK ecosystem market actors

Building on the UK ecosystem markets identified in the first stage of the review, relevant market actors were identified. For the purposes of this research, market actors were defined as UK ecosystem market entities and organizations who are involved in any aspect of these markets. In addition to the markets themselves, this included for example, relevant policy bodies, rural communities, advisors and intermediaries, landowners and managers, and investors.

Participants were recruited for an online workshop (facilitated in

Fig. 1. Overview of research design, showing the four methodological phases of the research.

May 2022) in collaboration with Scottish Government officials and researchers familiar with the range of interested actors interacting with ecosystem markets in Scotland and across the UK (authors had access to information that could identify individual participants during and after data collection). The workshop lasted for one hour, with participants writing comments simultaneously into a shared spreadsheet. It started with an introduction to the method by the facilitator, followed by a discussion to establish the boundaries of the analysis. This included the range of ecosystem markets to be included (based on the analysis in 2.1 above) and the geographical focus. The geographical focus was the whole of the UK, given the scale that these markets operate at, despite the fact that the workshop was funded by Scottish Government (hence the inclusion of only Scottish policy officials). To correct this bias, the four officials were supplemented with four researchers from Scottish institutions who had experience working across UK ecosystem markets. Following the workshop, participants were able to continue adding input to the analysis online, filling gaps where possible, and completing the data collection phase within two weeks of the workshop.

For each market actor identified, participants could add additional information they felt might be relevant using Reed et al.'s (2025) interest-influence-impact method for analysing relevant parties. Participants were invited to check each other's work, filling gaps in knowledge and offering alternative perspectives where relevant. They were also asked specifically to consider marginalised groups that may have been missed from the analysis (e.g., rural communities) and invited to suggest categories within which individual organisations could be grouped. Where organisations had more than one interest in high-integrity ecosystem markets, their primary interest was used. For example, RSPB develops nature-based solutions projects, some of which supply carbon offsets, but given the breadth of their interests across the natural capital policy agenda and their primary functions, they were classified as an environmental NGO rather than a project developer/offset provider.

2.3. Identifying ecosystem market principles relevant to the UK

Building on the analysis of UK ecosystem markets and market actors, we sought to identify principles for the development and operation of high-integrity ecosystem markets that could be applied to the UK to help guide the development of policy and governance mechanisms. This analysis drew on secondary sources, with previously published UK and international ecosystem market principles identified using a "snowball" sampling method with policy officials in Scotland and England and the British Standards Institute, until saturation was reached and no new documents containing market principles could be identified. For purposes of this search, 'international' encompassed documents developed for globally recognized markets; this did not include documents that pertain to markets operating in specific countries outside the UK. The following sources were identified as being relevant to the UK:

- UK sources:
 - o Defra's Nature Markets Policy Framework (Defra, 2023)
 - o Scottish Government's Interim Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital (Scottish Government, 2022a)
 - o Biodiversity Metric 4.0 (Natural England, 2021)
 - o The design of the UK's two most mature voluntary carbon markets, the Peatland Code version 2.0 (IUCN UK Peatland Programme,

2023) and the Woodland Carbon Code version 2.2 (Scottish Forestry, 2022)

- International sources:
 - o Integrity Council for the Voluntary Carbon Market (ICVCM)'s Core carbon principles consultation document (ICVCM, 2022);
 - o Voluntary Carbon Markets Integrity (VCMI) Initiative's Claims Code of Conduct (VCMI, 2023);
 - o Science-Based Targets Initiative (SBTi)'s Corporate Net-Zero Standard Version 1.0 (SBTi, 2021);
 - o Greenhouse Gas Protocol's Corporate Accounting and Reporting Standard (GHG Protocol, 2023, forthcoming);
 - o High level Integrity Principles for Biodiversity Markets (Plan Vivo, 2023)
 - o Global Biodiversity Standard (BGCI, SER, ICRAF, TRAFFIC, Ecosia, PVF and It.org, 2023)
 - o An international comparative analysis of 12 agricultural soil carbon codes and standards (Black et al., 2022);
 - o An international comparative analysis (based on Black et al.'s (2022) analytical framework) of three agroforestry and six salt-marsh codes and standards, funded by the Environment Agency's Natural Environment Investment Readiness Fund (Soil Association, 2024); and
 - o An international comparative analysis of approaches to measuring biodiversity in 25 biodiversity codes and standards, funded by NatureScot's Investment Readiness for Nature Scotland scheme (McVittie et al., 2023).

The analysis was conducted by the lead author and proceeded via the following steps:

1. Principles were extracted from each document and analysed using qualitative thematic analysis methods (Braun and Clarke, 2006) to identify themes inductively, grouping similar principles together;
2. Principles were screened for relevance to the UK context, removing principles that were not applicable in terms of their biophysical or cultural context (e.g. around working with first nations or indigenous groups);
3. Thematically grouped principles were then assessed qualitatively to identify each of the different concepts they contained, creating one point per concept (the bullet lists in Table S3, Supplementary Material). These individual points were then aggregated into a single summary point, which was then further condensed to form a single principle per thematic group, in the left-hand column of Table S3. Principles were linked to each of the sources that contained them in Table S3 (Supplementary Material).

Following this analysis, the co-authors refined the principles to ensure applicability across multiple ecosystem markets (for example, generalising by removing references to specific ecosystem services, habitats or land uses) and incorporated additional literature references in response to reviewer feedback.

3. Results

This section provides the findings of our analysis of ecosystem markets and their actors in the UK. This is followed by the results of a comparative analysis of principles for the development and operation of high-integrity ecosystem markets that could be applied by the actors

that were identified, to the markets found in the UK.

3.1. UK ecosystem markets overview

Broadly speaking, market activity can be split into insetting and offsetting (Fig. 2). Insetting is the practice of funding or carrying out activities to reduce impacts on the environment (e.g., greenhouse gas reduction or removal, or nature recovery projects) within an organisation’s own operations or supply chain, rather than relying on external projects that reduce impacts outside the organisations operations or supply chain. Insetting can take a number of forms. For example on land, shifts to regenerative farming practices and other methods that can reduce emissions or sequester and store carbon may be built into contracts between farmers and the companies they supply. In some cases, this may be a condition of contract that has no benefit for farmers other than giving them access to the ‘supply shed’ of a particular buyer. In other cases, contracts may include payments for costs of specific changes (e.g. seeds for cover crops, electric fencing and water systems for adaptive multi-paddock grazing), price premiums or (less commonly) carbon payments, alongside training and support. Alternatively, rather than contracting directly with farmers, companies seeking to reduce their scope 3 emissions may contract with groups of farmers through supply businesses or distributors (e.g. a cereals group or milk cooperative). Another approach is to buy carbon abatement certificates through project developer intermediaries, typically from the commodity/sector the company is operating in (but without traceability to farm level), with farmer paid per unit of carbon via the intermediary. Although many use their own proprietary governance and MRV, there are a growing number that use internationally recognised protocols that are also used for offsetting (e.g. Verra VM0042; Verra, 2023).

Insetting activity (left-hand side of Fig. 2) is being driven by a growing range of environmental, social and governance performance metrics (e.g. carbon foot printing, energy and water consumption, ESG risk management) and reporting standards for different types of voluntary disclosures. For example, the Task Force on Climate-Related Financial Disclosures (TCFD, 2023) provides a standardized framework for companies to disclose climate-related risks and opportunities in their financial filings, and it has seen a five-fold increase in adoption

since 2017. Building on this, the Task Force on Nature-Related Financial Disclosures (TNFD, 2023) released a beta framework for businesses to report wider nature-related risks. More broadly still, the International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB, 2023) aims to develop a global baseline of sustainability disclosures, and has created disclosure standards for sustainability-related financial information and climate-related disclosures. Other initiatives to guide ESG reporting include the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI, 2023), the Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP, 2023), the UK Green Taxonomy (GFI, 2023), the Competition and Market Authority Green Claims Code (Competition and Markets Authority, 2021), and the British Standards Institute’s PAS 2060 carbon neutrality standard (BSI, 2014).

Initiatives like the GHG Protocol (2023) and the Science-Based Targets Initiative (SBTi, 2021) can help companies link financial disclosures with science-based targets (that aim to limit global warming to well below 2 degrees Celsius above pre-industrial levels) and measurement protocols. They provide methods for target setting, risk assessment, measurement and reporting for Scope 1 (direct GHG emissions from sources that are owned or controlled by the reporting organization), Scope 2 (indirect GHG emissions associated with the generation of purchased electricity, heat, or steam consumed by the reporting organization) and Scope 3 (all other indirect GHG emissions that occur as a result of the organization’s activities, including those along the organization’s value chain) emissions. They include detailed guidance on how companies should account for and report GHG emissions and removals from land management, land use change and related activities (SBTi published revised Forest, Land and Agriculture Guidance (SBTi, 2022) and GHG Protocol will publish their revised guidance in 2024 (GHG Protocol, forthcoming). SBTi is now developing guidance for Beyond Value Chain Mitigation (BVCM; SBTi, 2023), to enable companies to go beyond their science-based targets and target climate action in projects that lie outside their supply chains. BVCM activities could include, for example:

- Emission reductions and/or carbon removals from farms supplying the commodities used by a company in a geographical area that includes the company’s suppliers (e.g. as part of an agricultural cooperative);

Fig. 2. Types of ecosystem market operating or close to market in the UK.

- As above but from farms closely connected to those that supply a company that does not grow the commodities that the company uses; and
- On land connected to a geographical area that supplies a company, connected environmentally and/or socio-economically, so that this land could indirectly benefit the sustainability or socio-economic status of the sourcing landscape, for example, peatland restoration or afforestation projects upstream in a catchment that could improve water quality or reduce flood risk in the sourcing landscape.

In addition to these voluntary initiatives, there are a number of regulatory requirements around ESG in the UK. For example, under the Companies Act 2006 (Strategic Report and Directors' Report) Regulations 2013, large UK-incorporated companies are required to disclose environmental information in their annual reports, including greenhouse gas emissions, energy consumption, water usage and waste generation. Under the Companies (Strategic Report) (Climate-related Financial Disclosure) Regulations 2021, these disclosures now have to align with TCFD guidelines. Financial Conduct Authority listing rules also require certain companies to state in annual reports whether they have made disclosures consistent with the TCFD framework.

In contrast to insetting (but similar to Beyond Value Chain Mitigation – see above), in offsetting (right-hand side of Fig. 2), emissions are reduced or carbon sequestered and stored outside the company's supply chain. Offset markets facilitate private investment in nature through the generation of units that can be bought and sold. They allow businesses to invest with farmers to enhance the ability of land and freshwater habitats to provide carbon storage, biodiversity uplift, clean water and other benefits. Four compliance markets were identified in our analysis, alongside seven types of voluntary carbon market and five other ecosystem markets. Of the compliance markets, there was only one for carbon, the UK Emissions Trading Scheme. Regulated by law, this scheme requires participants to comply with emissions reductions on a 'cap and trade' basis (Table S1, Supplementary Material). Although compliance carbon markets are reserved for the UK Government, the governments of Scotland, England, Northern Ireland and Wales can develop their own compliance biodiversity markets and have control over voluntary carbon and other voluntary ecosystem markets operating in their jurisdictions. Although the regulatory oversight of these markets is devolved to the individual countries and projects need to be developed in line with regulations in each jurisdiction, they operate as UK-wide markets accepting investment from companies based anywhere in the UK (some of the emerging markets also accept overseas investment).

England also operates compliance markets for biodiversity (Fig. 2, Table S1, Supplementary Material). Under Biodiversity Net Gain in England, developers must follow the mitigation hierarchy by first trying to avoid and minimize habitat loss. Then, if this is not possible, they must create habitat either on-site or off-site (calculated using Natural England's Biodiversity Metric 4.0; Natural England, 2021), purchase statutory credits from the government or purchase credits generated from habitat creation elsewhere in England. The introduction of the scheme was controversial, as it attempted to balance the simplicity and certainty demanded by the market with the complexity ecological systems and the need to ensure the ecological integrity of offsets (Gordon et al., 2015; Lockhart, 2015; Sobkowiak, 2020). As a result, there have been multiple revisions of the biodiversity metric in the years since its launch. The Scottish National Planning Framework 4 requires developers to protect, conserve, restore and enhance biodiversity in line with a mitigation hierarchy that prioritises biodiversity conservation and allows the restoration of degraded habitats to mitigate unavoidable damage (Scottish Government, 2023). It is currently exploring market-based approaches to deliver biodiversity gains that align with local ecological priorities. Defra are also developing Marine Net Gain in England that will work in a similar way to Biodiversity Net Gain, requiring all in-scope developments to leave the environment in a better state than before (Defra, 2022).

It is important to recognise the potential for regulatory divergence between different nations within the UK, where legislation from each country may make unique demands on these markets. Concerns have been raised about the potential for new taxes on ecosystem markets to distort the market (e.g. favouring investment in parts of the UK with lower taxes), and discussions are ongoing with HMRC and UK Treasury on taxes that may apply to landowners, project developers and retail aggregators who buy and sell on carbon credits, as well as companies who 'hold' credits on their books and how this is viewed in tax terms. Market distorting effects may also arise from mechanisms being considered to protect or share benefits with communities from natural capital markets in Scotland, if not adopted elsewhere in the UK. These are outlined in the recent "land reform in a net zero nation" consultation paper, in preparation for a future Land Reform Bill and a Community Wealth Building Bill, and include public interest tests for transfers of large-scale land holdings and community wealth funds (Scottish Government, 2022b).

There are numerous voluntary markets, either established or in development, in the UK. The majority of the codes and schemes that govern these markets focus on carbon, including woodland, peatland, agroforestry, carbon capture technologies, agricultural soils and blue carbon, although voluntary markets also exist for biodiversity, freshwater resources, ocean recovery and landscape recovery (Fig. 2, Table S1, Supplementary Material). The longest running voluntary carbon markets in the UK are the Woodland Carbon Code and the Peatland Code. Most codes and schemes focus on one market type, although Landscape Enterprise Networks (LENs) and other catchment management trading schemes deliver multiple ecosystem services as an integrated landscape-scale package, for example, including biodiversity, natural flood management and nutrient mitigation alongside actions to reduce emissions and sequester carbon. Also, Version 2.0 of the Peatland Code addresses the potential for integration of biodiversity and community benefits (NatureScot, 2022), both the Peatland Code and Woodland Carbon Code will soon be offering biodiversity units as part of an explicit bundle with carbon units or as separate units for projects not seeking carbon finance (IUCN UK Peatland Programme, 2025).

Codes and schemes vary widely in their approach to ensuring market integrity, in response to increasingly well-known flaws and credibility issues affecting voluntary markets (as summarised in the introduction). For example, some do not have transparent or standardised approaches to MRV or have MRV for individual projects reviewed on a case-by-case basis. Others have the governance and MRV components you would expect to see in a code, although they are not all fully transparent. Some companies combine project development, codes and registries within the same operation instead of using independent verification and registries. For example, there are at least eight companies now offering agricultural soil carbon credits, and some of these integrate functions that are traditionally separated to avoid conflicts of interest. Efforts are underway to standardize methodologies and establish minimum requirements for agricultural soil carbon markets through the British Standards Institute's Nature Market Standards programme (habitat and land-use specific guidance is planned to accompany BSI Flex 703 "Supply of nature-based carbon benefits").

3.2. UK ecosystem market actors

Over 200 organisations and groups were identified across 11 main categories in the analysis (Fig. 3). Table S2 (Supplementary Material) provides an overview of each category including examples of organisations and groups in each category and sub-category. Due to the sensitivity of some of the information collected about some organisations, only summary information is presented here. Categories with significant numbers of different organisations included (in descending order):

- Nature-based solutions project developers and offset/inset providers;

Fig. 3. Market actors with interests in the development of high-integrity ecosystem markets.

- Environmental/sustainability NGOs, thinktanks and representative organisations; and
- Landowner/manager NGOs, thinktanks and representative organisations.

Although fewer than ten organisations or groups were identified in a number of categories, these included important market actors, for example government departments and agencies (of which only a limited number have direct interests in natural capital and ecosystem markets). Some categories with apparently limited numbers of different actors were groups rather than organisations, where there are a limited number of representative organisations (e.g., tenant farmers).

3.3. Principles for the design and operation of high-integrity nature markets

A range of sources were identified (listed in the methods section) that proposed principles that could be used to define and/or govern high-integrity nature markets. Table 1 summarises each of the principles that emerged from the thematic analysis of these sources in three categories (for full results, see Table S3, Supplementary Material, where each principle followed by more detailed points drawn from across the sources, and the sources that featured the principle are listed):

1. Governance principles;
2. Measurement, reporting and verification principles; and
3. Wider benefits principles.

Although the majority of the principles apply to the design and operation of codes and schemes, a number of them also require engagement from other market actors within the governance hierarchy. As such, the principles are aimed at:

- Governments and their agencies acting within a single market or across multiple markets;

- Other governance bodies and mechanisms such as the UK Accreditation Service and the British Standards Institute;
- Codes and schemes operating within single markets or across multiple nature markets, including carbon, biodiversity, water quality and flood risk among others;
- Project owners and developers and others engaged in market infrastructure; and
- Investors and others engaged in market finance mechanisms.

To apply these principles, these different market actors will need to develop a range of policy, governance and market mechanisms, and these are discussed next.

4. Discussion

This paper has provided an overview of ecosystem markets currently operating in the UK, and the range of market actors with an interest in the development of high-integrity ecosystem markets. A comparative analysis of national and international principles for the development and operation of high-integrity markets led to the proposal of 15 principles pertaining to the governance, MRV and the wider benefits of well-run ecosystem markets (summarised in Table 1). However, to apply these principles at a national scale across multiple ecosystem markets, relationships between policy, governance, and market mechanisms and infrastructure need to be established in a coherent hierarchy (Fig. 4). For example, although codes and schemes can play an important role in applying these principles to the projects they facilitate and the buyers, sellers and intermediaries they interact with, there are questions around how the integrity of the codes and schemes themselves should be assessed. A consistent and coordinated approach to the development and operation of codes and schemes, as well as their accreditation and regulatory oversight is needed to ensure interactions between ecosystem services are managed at appropriate scales and feedback is provided to the policy community, where regulatory intervention is needed to protect the public interest.

Table 1
Summary of the principles that emerged from the analysis (for full details, see Table S3, Supplementary Material).

Principle	Summary
Market governance structures and procedures should be robust, coherent and transparent	Robust and transparent governance structures and procedures are needed around the ownership, management and operation of codes and schemes; monitoring, validation and enforcement; and the claims that buyers of units can make. High level coordination should occur across markets to ensure policy coherence, effectiveness and alignment across markets and relevant market actors.
Outcomes should not be double counted	Outcomes from projects should not be double counted and where more than one ecosystem service is being sold from the same activity in the same location ("stacking"), legal and financial additionality criteria should be passed in codes and schemes for each ecosystem service.
Outcomes should be additional	Ensuring that eligible practices and their expected outcomes are additional is essential to the integrity of nature markets, and high integrity codes and schemes typically include legal tests and at least one financial additionality test.
Outcomes should be permanent	Mechanisms should be in place to ensure that outcomes are effectively permanent. Permanence, or durability, relates to the length of time target ecosystem functions or services are maintained and the obligation to prevent or compensate for future reversals, for example via buffer pools and insurance products.
Damaging activities should not be moved elsewhere as a result of the project	Damaging activities, such as habitat degradation or GHG emissions, should not be displaced by the project, leading to negative outcomes elsewhere, and biodiversity projects should not displace existing biodiverse habitats, also known as leakage.
Transparent information should be available about validated projects and verified units	Codes and schemes should provide comprehensive and transparent information on all validated projects and units, available online for public scrutiny.
Standards should be in place to ensure ecological and administrative performance, triggering code governance and project management mechanisms to manage risks and uncertainty	Codes and schemes need to ensure successful performance at sites generating units. Code governance and project management elements need to account for risks and uncertainties that may affect the accrual of units over time (e.g., the likelihood that ecological targets will be achieved and the time it may take to yield self-sustaining and mature ecological functions/services).
Units sold within nature markets should be clearly defined and based on appropriate and evidence-based assessments of outcomes	The selection of eligible practices and assessment of likely and actual outcomes from projects needs to be evidence-based. Codes should define appropriate and ecologically relevant units, metrics and assessment approaches that holistically address ecological outcomes and changes in relevant ecosystem functions or services.
Validation and verification of projects and outcomes should be robust and independent	The validation of projects and verification of outcomes should be robust and independent.
There should be environmental and social safeguards	Codes and schemes should ensure projects do no harm, proactively managing risks and trade-offs with other ecosystem services, local communities and other rights holders.

Table 1 (continued)

Principle	Summary
Environmental and social net positive impacts may also be required	Codes and schemes may require projects to deliver net social and environmental benefits beyond the benefits arising from the generation of units, where possible as part of a wider place-based approach to the coordination of public and private payments for ecosystem services at landscape, seascape and/or catchment scales.
Engagement should take place with all relevant parties affected by projects	All relevant parties should be actively engaged in both the development of governance mechanisms and individual projects to ensure they have an opportunity to comment on and shape both projects and the codes and schemes that govern them.
Markets should be as easy and low risk to access as possible	Codes and schemes should be as simple as possible within the bounds of the rules and systems needed to maintain market integrity, which should be provided by public bodies who should also provide clarity around interactions with regulations, tax and public funding and where possible prioritise public funding to address market failures and de-risk market engagement for buyers, sellers and intermediaries.
Markets should be open to innovation	Developers of governance mechanisms, codes and schemes, and owners and operators of market infrastructure should be open to innovation as new technologies and advancements in scientific understanding emerge.

Within the hierarchy summarised in Fig. 4 and further detailed in Fig. 5, it is possible to identify a number of governance mechanisms through which market principles may be applied. At the bottom of the governance hierarchy in Fig. 5 is an assurance framework that seeks to assure the delivery of high-integrity projects through a combination of regulatory, market and project-based mechanisms. At the bottom of the assurance framework in Fig. 5, are the projects that deliver ecosystem services, and the project developers, intermediaries and brokers that make these projects possible (the bottom two rows in Fig. 5). A approaches to project management can vary considerably, for example in relation to the extent to which work is carried out by landowners, their tenants or external contractors. As such, there is a need for governance mechanisms that can bring a level of standardisation around minimum integrity levels, manage risks and ensure efficient and effective project delivery.

Market infrastructure (the next level in the hierarchy in Fig. 5) by managing project risks and ensuring delivery of outcomes from projects. For example, this may include ensuring that there are robust contracts in place, there is effective project management, or insurance products to protect buyers and/or sellers against non-delivery, typically as a result of factors beyond the control of the project. This market infrastructure may be used by projects, as well as by market codes and verification bodies (further up the hierarchy, Fig. 5), enabling them to support the development and delivery of high-integrity projects at scale.

Sitting above market infrastructure in the hierarchy in Fig. 5 is the need for regulation, as there is a risk of misleading or fraudulent activity in these markets, especially given the intangible nature of the outputs being marketed. Concerns have been raised on both the supply and demand sides of the market. For example, demand-side actors may make unsubstantiated claims about the benefits arising from their investment. Although inadequate on its own, the UK Advertising Standards Authority (ASA) and the Committee of Advertising Practice issued guidance on "The environment: misleading claims and social responsibility in advertising" (ASA, 2023), and advertisements can be banned if they

Fig. 4. Overview of ecosystem market hierarchy.

	Governance mechanism	Description	Example	
Generalisable	Market principles and reporting guidelines	Minimum requirements for the design and operation of high-integrity ecosystem markets and corporate reporting in a given jurisdiction (or internationally)	ICVCM Core Carbon Principles may be supplemented with other market principles (e.g. stipulating responsible investment principles or community benefits) to create a UK principles standard to bring consistency to standards for specific ecosystem services, habitats and land uses	Standards framework
	Policy co-ordination group	Co-ordination between policy and expert groups	Regular meeting between expert group chairs and key policy teams	
	Aggregation, integration and blending mechanisms	Place-based mechanisms to aggregate supply & demand, co-ordinate ecosystem service delivery in space and stack (private) or blend (public) payments for multiple services at project design	Landscape Enterprise Networks, do this at regional scales and could be adapted and/or scaled. Stacking and blending is currently operationalized via additionality criteria of codes and full stack must be agreed pre-contract. New options to blend public funding and private finance are under development in the UK	
Land use or habitat-specific	Operation of standards setting minimum requirements for codes operating in each habitat, land use and ecosystem service	Expert groups set minimum requirements (e.g. for additionality and permanence), list approved methods (e.g. carbon models and MRV sampling regimes) and evaluate codes, updating requirements as evidence becomes available	BSI establishes a carbon standard, with more detailed standards for specific habitats and land uses, against which the integrity of codes can be evaluated. For example, for agricultural soil carbon this could include a minimum permanence period, minimum soil sampling depth, approved models to estimate carbon in project design documents	Assurance framework
	Accreditation of codes to relevant standards	Individual codes and schemes are checked to ensure they comply with relevant standards (above)	The Woodland Carbon Code is accredited to ICROA, and both it and the Peatland Code are applying for accreditation to ICVCM's Core Carbon Principles, and in future will accredit to relevant BSI standards	
	Individual codes	A document, or set of documents, that set out the requirements and rules to establish and run a project that aims to generate verifiable carbon or other ecosystem credits	The Woodland Carbon Code and Peatland Code, and other codes under development, e.g. hedgerows, agricultural soils, saltmarsh and agroforestry	
	Verification bodies	Organisations that validate projects and verify ecosystem service claims of projects against the requirements of individual codes	OF&G is a verification body for the Peatland Code and Woodland Carbon Code which is accredited by UKAS to ISO 14064/3 and 14065	
	Financial and claims regulation	Protection from fraud, ensuring healthy competition and buyer-integrity checks to avoid unsubstantiated or misleading claims	The UK Financial Conduct Authority could extend its jurisdiction to ecosystem markets and the Companies Act could be adapted to require the UK's largest companies to align with VCM's Claims Code	
	Market infrastructure	Market registries, online marketplaces, model contracts, legal mechanisms and insurance	UK Land Carbon Registry and insurance exist with new marketplaces, investment platforms, contractual models and insurance products being developed	
	Project developers, intermediaries and brokers	Organisations that may develop projects under codes, sourcing both buyers (e.g. offsetters) and sellers (e.g. landowners)	Forest Carbon Ltd develops peatland and woodland projects and sells or retires credits via the UK Land Carbon Registry	
	Projects generating ecosystem services	Interventions undertaken in a geographically defined area to sequester carbon, avoid emissions and/or deliver other ecosystem services that adhere to a relevant code	Carrick Peatland (restoration project) developed by Tillhill Forestry	

Developed and in operation (Green box) Under development (Yellow box)

Fig. 5. Governance hierarchy showing mechanisms that may increase the integrity of ecosystem markets internationally, illustrated with current and planned examples from the UK.

make misleading climate claims. **VCMi's (2023) Claims Code of Conduct** was developed to prevent unreliable or misleading offset claims, and ensure claims are backed by rigorous measurement, reporting and verification. However, questions remain about how this is

operationalised in any given jurisdiction. For example, **VCMi's Code** could be used directly or be adapted for application in the UK via a BSI standard. There are also questions about whether buyer integrity checks should be voluntary or mandatory. If mandatory, questions arise over

how to enforce accreditation of buyers to VCMI, and how this is funded to ensure SMEs and Third Sector organisations have access to carbon markets. For example, enforcement could require buyers to be VCMI accredited (minimum silver claim level) to open a buyer account on registries, with buyer privileges suspended if VCMI certification is lost. Public funding may be needed to pay for SMEs and Third Sector organisations to build capacity/readiness for achieving VCMI certification, potentially devising a national scheme where larger companies pay higher sums to make it possible to offer reduced fees to smaller companies and charities.

In addition to this, there are concerns that supply-side actors might sell the same carbon abatement to multiple buyers or engage in other fraudulent activity. As a result, financial regulation may be needed in ecosystem markets, for example, extending the jurisdiction of bodies like the Financial Conduct Authority in the UK to include ecosystem markets. This alone, however, would not be sufficient to protect the integrity of ecosystem markets, because regulators only get involved when there is evidence of wrongdoing. Given that the first verification point under many carbon codes is not until year five, if significant issues were uncovered at this point, in large enough schemes, this could significantly undermine wider market confidence.

Moving from the assurance framework (the lower portion of Fig. 5) to the standards framework (upper portion Fig. 5), governance moves from the operation of individual codes and their verification bodies, to the operation of standards against which the integrity of codes (and the projects that sit under them) can be evaluated. With sufficient funding and expertise, it may be possible to create a robust set of codes for different ecosystem services, land uses and habitats, that are evidence-based and effectively managed. For peatlands and woodlands, code development has been led in the UK by governmental agencies, and is now proceeding for other land uses and habitats via both publicly funded initiatives (e.g., the development of a Saltmarsh Code, funded by Defra) and market activity (e.g., see the soil carbon schemes in Table S1, Supplementary Material).

However, the quality of market-derived codes varies, so it is necessary to devise mechanisms to ensure minimum standards against which the integrity of codes and the verification bodies they work with can be evaluated (“accreditation of codes to relevant standards” in Fig. 5). For example, codes and schemes may seek accreditation to the International Carbon Reduction and Offset Alliance (ICROA) or ICVCM’s Core Carbon Principles, and verification bodies may directly certify or achieve accredited certification to ISO and other standards, for example via bodies like the UK Accreditation Service. However, while such certification processes typically provide robust assessments of the governance arrangements of codes and schemes and their overall approach to MRV (for example, ensuring models and other methods are based on peer-reviewed literature), there is limited scrutiny of the science driving their MRV (e.g., the validity of emissions factors developed on the basis of measurements that are biased to certain locations or habitats) and the details of its implementation (e.g., the depth to which soil carbon measurements should be taken). Moreover, while ICVCM’s Principles are widely regarded as the benchmark for high integrity carbon markets internationally, they have been developed to work internationally, with an emphasis on lower income contexts, where the majority of projects are located. As a result, they offer limited requirements on community engagement (e.g., around the inclusivity of engagement, methods for avoiding consultation fatigue), benefit-sharing (e.g., around the transparency of benefit creation and sharing, and the proportionality of benefits relative to project impacts or revenues), grievance processes (e.g., ensuring all market intermediaries provide access to grievance processes for full project durations) and do not mandate the same level of transparency around project finance and revenues, ongoing social impacts, or stacking of credits between multiple programmes, instead leaving many procedural and distributional details to the discretion of individual programs.

For this reason, in the UK, a more detailed set of standards with

minimum requirements for high-integrity codes is being developed by BSI across a range of ecosystem services (including climate change mitigation, biodiversity and water quality), with the carbon standard (BSI Flex 703) linking to guidance for specific land uses (e.g., arable or grassland soils) and habitats (e.g., peatlands and woodlands; BSI, 2023). Although this set of more detailed, country-specific standards sits above relevant international in the governance hierarchy (in Fig. 5), the BSI carbon standard has been designed to align with ICVCM’s Core Carbon Principles and ICROA, opening up the possibility of fast tracking accreditation for programmes that have met the requirements of either standard. Recommendations for the first set of land use or habitat level minimum requirements for carbon markets has been developed for agricultural soil carbon (Black et al., 2022). Once fully developed, it will be possible to accredit codes against these minimum standards, providing clear market signals to investors and project developers alike, so that they work with the most reputable codes. In addition to stimulating demand, it is hoped that this will also increase the supply of projects to market, given increasingly well documented concerns from landowners and managers about the dangers of engaging with carbon markets (e.g., Reed et al., 2024a; Ingram et al., in press). However, there are limits to how often a BSI standard can be updated in response to new evidence, and there is no mechanism to horizon scan for negative unintended consequences as markets comply with the new standards. Moreover, there is a danger that each ecosystem service and habitat is managed separately, in contrast to the interdependencies that exist in the real-world.

For this reason, it is important to design feedback mechanisms that could help policy teams identify market failures and plan regulatory responses where needed (“aggregation, integration and blending mechanisms” in Fig. 5). Mechanisms for aggregating both supply and demand for ecosystem services may also be needed; different investors may be looking for contradictory outcomes and land holdings may be highly fragmented and so not investible at sufficient scale. These mechanisms need to be place-based because actual landscapes (and seascapes) integrate multiple uses and habitats, and produce many different ecosystem services. Some interventions will produce one ecosystem service at the expense of another, cancelling out benefits from different schemes and investors. In addition to thinking about how private payments for ecosystem services interact in space, it is also important to think carefully about how private and public payments interact, and avoid situations where public funding crowds out private investment.

Next, it is important to ensure there is a level of policy coordination within and across ecosystem markets to avoid market distorting policies and subsidies, and other negative unintended interactions between policies and markets. In many European countries, ecosystem markets operate at sub-national scales, which is similar to the challenges posed by the UK’s four countries, given that voluntary ecosystem markets are devolved to these administrations. Even where policy is national, there is a need to ensure the various government departments and delivery agencies are aligned. Where there is potential for divergent regulatory constraints, such as a requirement for projects to contribute to community wealth funds, or tax regimes for example, there is the potential for competition between jurisdictions and a race to the bottom.

Finally, at the top of the governance hierarchy in Fig. 5, to bring consistency across all of these policy and governance mechanisms, there is a need for high-level principles that can operate across markets for different ecosystem services in different habitats. In addition to minimum expectations around additionality, leakage and permanence contained in BSI’s “overarching principles and framework” standard (BSI Flex 701; BSI, 2025), there is a requirement for programmes to accredit to their “community engagement and benefits from natural capital projects” standard (BSI Flex 705) (BSI, 2023).

In so doing, it may be possible to address procedural and distributional justice issues, which have been largely ignored in the ecosystem market research, but which often exacerbate existing inequalities,

further concentrating power and resources (IPBES, 2022; Loos et al., 2023; CCC, 2023). By perpetuating existing power imbalances, current governance structures give communities a limited voice or agency around changes in land use that ultimately shape their future. Jack et al. (2008) suggested that ecosystem markets are likely to benefit the poorest in society if these groups are able to provide ecosystem services with the lowest opportunity cost, but such groups rarely own land and so are blocked from directly benefiting from these markets. Instead, Calvet-Mir et al. (2015) identified a trade-off between efficiency and equity in ecosystem markets, where most markets prioritise efficiency (the achievement of environmental outcomes at the lowest possible price) at the expense of socially equitable and just outcomes. The cost-minimising approach of these markets can therefore perpetuate inequality and further marginalise vulnerable groups. This can include smallholders who do not have the economies of scale necessary to be able to compete with larger landowners to provide ecosystem services cost-effectively. As a result, Chan et al. (2017) proposed the development of ecosystem market mechanisms that can benefit smallholders, and Costanza et al. (2021) proposed a Common Asset Trust and the Costa Rican Government created a National Forestry Fund (Pagiola, 2008; Porras et al., 2013), where the government attracts and then distributes private finance to a range of sellers, which could include both smallholders and tenants. Similarly, Common Asset Trusts are also being explored as a governance framework for marine and ocean ecosystems, highlighting their potential applicability across a wide range of environmental contexts (Quatrini & Costanza, 2023).

Community engagement has often acted as a conduit for reducing inequality in top-down decision making in bottom-up ecosystem restoration (Fritz et al., 2024). However, the failure to recognise the impact that this top-down approach has on reducing engagement to participation and therefore decentralising the role of community in decisions making processes has been discussed and identified at a global scale (Ojha et al., 2016; Solman et al., 2021). The Scottish Government's Natural Capital Market Framework (Scottish Government, 2024), has a strong emphasis on both engagement and community benefit. Going beyond public benefit (e.g., clean air, and biodiversity), community benefit is defined as tangible and measurable mechanisms that provide intentional social and economic advantages provided to local communities through land ownership, use, and management (Scottish Land Commission, 2023). In addition, the Scottish Land Commission state that these benefits should be deliberate and have substantial long-term delivery that are sustained beyond the scope of the project to ensure sustainable impact to the community.

Community benefit have already been delivered in key areas of the green energy transition across Scotland (MacDonald et al., 2017; Määttä, 2024) but are often reliant on the voluntary implementation of good practice principles (such as those provided by Scottish Government, 2019). As discussed by Reed et al. (2022, 2024b), community benefit requires responsible scaling and coordination to ensure that the benefits of nature-based markets are not only accessed by buyers, project developers and landowners, and provide more inclusive benefits to a range of community beneficiaries and other relevant parties affected by natural capital projects. There are however challenges to doing this in practice, as illustrated by the recent case study of community benefits from the restoration and management of the UK's largest national park, the Cairngorm's National Park (Daniels-Creasey, 2024). An assessment of the delivery of community benefit identified three key areas of success:

1. Employment and training: Restoration projects created jobs in forestry, conservation, and estate management, but many were short-term or seasonal.
2. Community engagement: Some landowners made efforts to involve communities in planning or provide public access to restored land.
3. Education and volunteering: Projects offered school programs and volunteering opportunities to build environmental awareness.

However, as discussed by Daniels-Creasey (2024), key challenges were identified in the implementation of these benefits. For example, while some projects created short-term jobs or volunteering opportunities, a clear lack of lasting economic or social improvements for local communities were identified. Furthermore, local participation in the planning and implementation of restoration efforts was limited with decisions about land use change, such as woodland expansion or peatland restoration. Additionally, a lack of transparency regarding project objectives, funding sources (particularly private finance for carbon or biodiversity credits), and the expected long-term impacts was identified. As such, the governance of community benefit is likely to require (Table S3):

- Clear principles for mapping and understanding the diversity of local communities, including the identification of marginalized or vulnerable groups and the cultural or historical contexts within which they operate;
- Systematic assessments of likely impacts of projects (both benefits and negative impacts) for communities, alongside transparent communication of relevant project information in an accessible and timely manner, alongside a documented system for receiving and addressing community feedback;
- Resourcing to build sufficient capacity for community involvement that addresses barriers to participation for different groups within the community;
- Co-designed benefit sharing arrangements (explicitly linked to impact assessments) that maintain or enhance existing benefits and mitigate adverse effects of projects alongside the generation of new benefits;
- Proportionate approaches to benefit distribution, where the depth and breadth of engagement and community benefit reflect the scale of the project and surplus revenues generated; and
- Ongoing monitoring and evaluation of community involvement and benefit provision, using evidence-based metrics that enable adaptive management of engagement and benefits.

Although the governance hierarchy in Figs. 4 and 5 was developed primarily with reference to offset markets, there are similar challenges with insets. Future work needs to provide guidance around the integrity of measurement, reporting and verification in insets, their permanence, and the potential for negative unintended consequences from investments in insetting. For example, there are few standardised approaches to MRV with current farm-level "calculators" varying in their levels of transparency and rigour. Although it will be possible to apply the BSI carbon standard to both offsetting and insetting activities, it is not clear whether there is sufficient interest in increasing the integrity of insets for companies to invest in higher integrity approaches that are more aligned with best practice in offset markets. Moreover, the majority of companies that are insetting have complex global supply chains, and so are looking to align with international standards that can be applied across their value chain rather than engaging with jurisdiction-specific governance mechanisms.

In conclusion, the principles proposed in this paper have the potential to bring integrity and coherence to ecosystem markets at a national scale. They build on international initiatives, creating consistency across global voluntary markets, whilst drawing on national experience in the design and operation of high-integrity codes like the Woodland Carbon Code and the Peatland Code. Taken together, the market principles and governance hierarchy could be used to ensure the development of high-integrity ecosystem markets across the UK and internationally, as national governments around the world attempt to responsibly build and scale these markets.

As such, there are now calls for ecosystem markets to go beyond ensuring "no net harm", to delivering community benefits (Calvet-Mir et al., 2015; Yu et al., 2020; Scottish Government, 2022a, Bremer et al., 2023), which we define (after Scottish Land Commission, 2023) as

intentional benefits, arising from investment in ecosystem services, provided on a negotiated basis for the long-term benefit of place-based communities. As the range of ecosystem markets expands and the marketplace becomes more complex, there is an urgent need to identify policy and governance options that could facilitate the design and operation of high-integrity ecosystem markets that generate real, verifiable, additional and permanent environmental and societal benefits. The International Council for Voluntary Carbon Markets have proposed core carbon principles (ICVCM, 2023), the Voluntary Carbon Markets Initiative have developed a Claims Code of Practice to counter greenwashing (VCMI, 2023) and there are a range of other international initiatives to increase the integrity of other types of ecosystem markets (e.g., high level biodiversity principles proposed by Plan Vivo, 2023).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Mark S. Reed: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Julia M. McCarthy:** Writing – original draft. **Eric A. Jensen:** Writing – review & editing. **Rosie Everett:** Writing – review & editing. **Hannah Rudman:** Writing – original draft.

Declaration of competing interest

MR is Research Lead for IUCN UK Peatland Programme, a member of the Executive Board of the Peatland Code, a member of the agriculture and land use working group of the Just Transition Commission, an unpaid/volunteer board member for Huntly Development Trust, co-chairs UNEP's Global Peatland Initiative Research Working Group and is CEO of Fast Track Impact, part of the Institute for Methods Innovation. JM and RE have no conflicts of interest. EJ has worked on consultancy projects for UNESCO, the UK's Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs, Chester Zoo, Scotland's Centre of Expertise for Waters (CREW), and other government departments, agencies and non-profit organizations relevant to this paper in the UK and internationally. He is CEO of the Institute for Methods Innovation, which has a broad range of clients and trainees relevant to this paper, including UK and international government representatives working on related topics. HR is a non-executive board director of Highlands Rewilding Ltd., a member of the UNEP/WEF Biodiversity Credit Alliance's Taskforce and an advisor to Agrimetrics.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2025.101760>.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

References

- ASA, 2023. The environment: misleading claims and social responsibility in advertising. Available at: <https://www.asa.org.uk/advice-online/environmental-claims-carbon-offsetting-and-carbon-neutral.html>.
- Bakker, K., 2005. Neoliberalizing nature? Market environmentalism in water supply in England and Wales. *Ann. Assoc. Am. Geogr.* 95 (3), 542–565.
- BGCI, SER, ICRAF, TRAFFIC, Ecosia, PVF, It.org, 2023. The Global Biodiversity Standard: technical consultation. Available at: <https://www.biodiversitystandard.org/the-technical-consultation/>.
- Black, H.L.J., Reed, M.S., Kendall, H., Parkhurst, R., Cannon, N., Chapman, P.J., Orman, M., Phelps, J., Rudman, H., Whaley, S., Yeluripati, J.B., 2022. What makes an operational Farm Soil Carbon Code? Insights from a global comparison of existing soil carbon codes using a structured analytical framework. *Carbon Manage.* 13, 554–580.
- Braun, V., Clarke, V., 2006. Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qual. Res. Psychol.* 3, 77–101.
- Bremer, L.L., Nelson, S., Jackson, S., Izquierdo-Tort, S., Lansing, D., Shapiro-Garza, E., Echavarría, M., Upton, C., Asquith, N., Isyaku, U., Asiyambi, A., 2023. Embedding local values in payments for ecosystem services for transformative change. *Curr. Opin. Environ. Sustain.* 64, 101354.
- BSI, 2014. PAS 2060 Carbon Neutrality: Supporting the energy revolution towards net zero. Available at: <https://www.bsigroup.com/en-GB/pas-2060-carbon-neutrality/>.
- BSI, 2023. A high-integrity standards framework for UK nature markets, British Standards Institute. Available at: <https://www.bsigroup.com/en-GB/about-bsi/uk-national-standards-body/sustainability-and-climate-action/nature-investment/a-high-integrity-standards-framework-for-uk-nature-markets/>.
- BSI (2025) BSI Flex 701 Nature Markets - Overarching Principles and Framework. Available at: <https://www.bsigroup.com/en-GB/insights-and-media/insights/brochures/bsi-flex-701-nature-markets-overarching-principles-and-framework/>.
- Cadman, T., Hales, R., 2022. COP26 and a framework for future global agreements on carbon market integrity. *Int. J. Soc. Qual.* 12 (1), 76–99.
- Calvet-Mir, L., Corbera, E., Martin, A., Fisher, J., Gross-Camp, N., 2015. Payments for ecosystem services in the tropics: a closer look at effectiveness and equity. *Curr. Opin. Environ. Sustain.* 14, 150–162.
- CDP, 2023. Carbon Disclosure Project. Available at: <https://www.cdp.net/en>.
- Chan, K.M., Anderson, E., Chapman, M., Jespersen, K., Olmsted, P., 2017. Payments for ecosystem services: rife with problems and potential—for transformation towards sustainability. *Ecol. Econ.* 140, 110–122.
- Committee on Climate Change, 2022. Voluntary Carbon Markets and Offsetting. Available at: <https://www.theccc.org.uk/publication/voluntary-carbon-markets-and-offsetting/>.
- Competition and Markets Authority, 2021. Green claims code: making environmental claims. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/green-claims-code-making-environmental-claims>.
- Convention on Biological Diversity, 2022. Nations Adopt Four Goals, 23 Targets for 2030 In Landmark UN Biodiversity Agreement. Available at: <https://www.cbd.int/article/cop15-cbd-press-release-final-19dec2022>.
- Costanza, R., Atkins, P.W., Hernandez-Blanco, M., Kubiszewski, I., 2021. Common asset trusts to effectively steward natural capital and ecosystem services at multiple scales. *J. Environ. Manage.* 280, 111801.
- CreditNature, 2023. Nature impact tokens. Available at: <https://crednature.com/nature-impact-tokens/>.
- Daniels-Creasey, A. (2024). Delivering community benefits from nature restoration projects in the Cairngorms National Park. A report for Scottish Land Commission. Available at: https://www.landcommission.gov.scot/downloads/66ea83951ba3d_Delivering%20community%20benefits%20from%20nature%20restoration%20projects%20in%20the%20Cairngorms%20National%20Park.pdf.
- Defra, 2022. Consultation on the Principles of Marine Net Gain. Available at: <https://consult.defra.gov.uk/defra-net-gain-consultation-team/consultation-on-the-principles-of-marine-net-gain/>.
- Defra, 2023. Nature markets: A framework for scaling up private investment in nature recovery an sustainable farming. Available at: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/1147397/nature-markets.pdf.
- EnTrade, 2023. About EnTrade. Available at: <https://www.entrade.co.uk/about-us>.
- Ferreira, C., 2017. The contested instruments of a new governance regime: accounting for nature and building markets for biodiversity offsets. *Account. Audit. Account. J.* 30 (7), 1568–1590.
- Fritz, L., Baum, C.M., Low, S., Sovacool, B.K., 2024. Public engagement for inclusive and sustainable governance of climate interventions. *Nat. Commun.* 15 (1), 4168.
- GFI, 2023. UK Green Taxonomy – GTAG. Available at: <https://www.greenfinanceinstitute.com/programmes/uk-green-taxonomy-gtag/>.
- GHG Protocol, 2023. Corporate Accounting and Reporting Standard. Available at: <https://ghgprotocol.org/sites/default/files/standards/ghg-protocol-revised.pdf>.
- GHG Protocol, Forthcoming. Land Sector and Removals Guidance. Available at: <https://ghgprotocol.org/land-sector-and-removals-guidance>.
- Gordon, A., Bull, J.W., Wilcox, C., Maron, M., 2015. Perverse incentives risk undermining biodiversity offset policies. *J. Appl. Ecol.* 52 (2), 532–537.

- Greenhalgh, T., Thorne, S., Malterud, K., 2018. Time to challenge the spurious hierarchy of systematic over narrative reviews? *Eur. J. Clin. Invest.* 48 (6), e12931.
- GRI, 2023. The global standards for sustainability impacts. Available at: <https://www.globalreporting.org/standards/>.
- ICVCM, 2023. Core carbon principles. Section 4: Assessment Framework. Available at: <https://icvcm.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/CCP-Section-4-FINAL-27Mar23.pdf>.
- Ingram, J., Reed, M.S., Maye, D., In press. Contestations in the emerging soil-based carbon economy: towards a research agenda. *Sustainability Science*.
- IPBES, 2022. Summary for policymakers of the methodological assessment of the diverse values and valuation of nature of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. In: Pascual, U., Balvanera, P., Christie, M., Baptiste, B., González-Jiménez, D., Anderson, C.B., Athayde, S., Chaplin-Kramer, R., Jacobs, S., Kelemen, E., Kumar, R., Lazos, E., Martin, A., Mwampamba, T.H., Nakangu, B., O'Farrell, P., Raymond, C.M., Subramanian, S.M., Termansen, M., Van Noordwijk, M., Vatn, A. (eds) IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany, p 37. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6522392>.
- IPCC, 2023. AR6 Synthesis Report: Climate Change 2023. Available at: <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/syr/>.
- IPCC, 2018. Global Warming of 1.5°C. An IPCC Special Report on the Impacts of Global Warming of 1.5°C Above Pre-industrial Levels and Related Global Greenhouse Gas Emission Pathways, in the Context of Strengthening the Global Response to the Threat of Climate Change, Sustainable Development, and Efforts to Eradicate Poverty, eds V. Masson-Delmotte, P. Zhai, H. O. Pörtner, D. Roberts, J. Skea, P. R. Shukla, A. Pirani, W. Moufouma-Okia, C. Péan, R. Pidcock, S. Connors, J. B. R. Matthews, Y. Chen, X. Zhou, M. I. Gomis, E. Lonnoy, T. Maycock, M. Tignor, and T. Waterfiel.
- IPCC, 2022. *Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability*. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [Pörtner, H.-O., D.C. Roberts, M. Tignor, E.S. Poloczanska, K. Mintenbeck, A. Alegría, M. Craig, S. Langsdorf, S. Lösschke, V. Möller, A. Okem, and B. Rama (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA. doi:10.1017/9781009325844.
- IUCN UK Peatland Programme, 2023. Peatland Code Version 2.0. Available at: <https://www.iucn-uk-peatlandprogramme.org/peatland-code-0>.
- IUCN UK Peatland Programme, 2025. Public Consultation for Biodiversity Quantification Methodology. Available at: <https://www.iucn-uk-peatlandprogramme.org/news/public-consultation-biodiversity-quantification-methodology>.
- ISSB, 2023. International Sustainability Standards Board. Available at: <https://www.ifrs.org/groups/international-sustainability-standards-board/>.
- Jack, B.K., Kousky, C., Sims, K.R., 2008. Designing payments for ecosystem services: Lessons from previous experience with incentive-based mechanisms. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 105 (28), 9465–9470.
- KPMG, 2024. *The move to mandatory reporting: KPMG Survey of Sustainability Reporting 2024*. KPMG International. Available at: <https://kpmg.com/sg/en/home/insights/2024/11/the-move-to-mandatory-reporting-survey-of-sustainability-reporting-2024.html> [Accessed 27 Mar. 2025].
- Kroeger, T., Casey, F., 2007. An assessment of market-based approaches to providing ecosystem services on agricultural lands. *Ecol. Econ.* 64 (2), 321–332.
- Lockhart, A., 2015. Developing an offsetting programme: tensions, dilemmas and difficulties in biodiversity market-making in England. *Environ. Conserv.* 42 (4), 335–344.
- Loos, J., Benra, F., Berbés-Blázquez, M., Bremer, L.L., Chan, K.M., Egho, B., Felipe-Lucia, M., Geneletti, D., Keeler, B., Locatelli, B., Loft, L., 2023. An environmental justice perspective on ecosystem services. *Ambio* 52 (3), 477–488.
- Määttä, S., 2024. Community-developer collaboration and voluntary community benefits in Scotland: are community benefits a gift or compensation? *Energy Policy* 191, 114164.
- Macdonald, C., Glass, J., Creamer, E., 2017. What is the benefit of community benefits? Exploring local perceptions of the provision of community benefits from a commercial wind energy project. *Scott. Geogr. J.* 133 (3–4), 172–191.
- McVittie, A., Cole, L., McCarthy, J., Fisher, H., and Rudman, H. (2023) Research into Approaches to Measuring Biodiversity in Scotland, Final Report to Scottish Government. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/research-approach-es-measuring-biodiversity-scotland/documents/>.
- Muradian, R., Corbera, E., Pascual, U., Kosoy, N., May, P.H., 2010. Reconciling theory and practice: an alternative conceptual framework for understanding payments for environmental services. *Ecol. Econ.* 69 (6), 1202–1208.
- NatureScot, 2022. Investment Ready Nature Scotland (IRNS) Grant Scheme – successful projects. Available online at: <https://www.nature.scot/doc/investment-ready-nature-scotland-irns-grant-scheme-successful-projects>.
- Nash, K.L., Cvitanovic, C., Fulton, E.A., Halpern, B.S., Milner-Gulland, E.J., Watson, R.A., Blanchard, J.L., 2017. Planetary boundaries for a blue planet. *Nat. Ecol. Evol.* 1 (11), 1625–1634.
- Natural England, 2021. The Biodiversity Metric 4.0 (JP039). Available at: <https://publications.naturalengland.org.uk/publication/6049804846366720>.
- Ojha, H.R., Ford, R., Keenan, R.J., Race, D., Vega, D.C., Baral, H., Sapkota, P., 2016. Delocalizing communities: changing forms of community engagement in natural resources governance. *World Dev.* 87, 274–290.
- Pagiola, S., 2008. Payments for environmental services in Costa Rica. *Ecol. Econ.* 65 (4), 712–724.
- Petticrew, M., Rehfuess, E., Noyes, J., Higgins, J.P., Mayhew, A., Pantoja, T., Shemilt, I., Sowden, A., 2013. Synthesizing evidence on complex interventions: how meta-analytical, qualitative, and mixed-method approaches can contribute. *J. Clin. Epidemiol.* 66 (11), 1230–1243.
- Plan Vivo, 2023. High level Integrity Principles for Biodiversity Markets. Available at: <https://www.planvivo.org/Handlers/Download.ashx?IDMF=a7c1bcf0-7602-408b-b93b-907a6e9ba7ad>.
- Porras, I., Barton, D.N., Miranda, M., Chacón-Cascante, A., 2013. Learning from 20 years of Payments for Ecosystem Services in Costa Rica. International Institute for Environment and Development, London.
- Quatrini, S., 2021. Challenges and opportunities to scale up sustainable finance after the COVID-19 crisis: Lessons and promising innovations from science and practice. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 48, 101240.
- Quatrini, S., Costanza, R., 2023. In: No Time to Lie: Sustainable Finance Needs Nextgen Assurance. Routledge, pp. 77–99.
- Reed, M.S., Curtis, T., Kendall, H., Gosal, A., Andersen, S.P., Ziv, G., Attlee, A., Hay, M., Hill, D., Martin-Ortega, J., Martino, S., Olesen, A.S., Prior, S., Rodgers, C., Rudman, H., Tanneberger, F., Waylen, K., 2022. Integrating ecosystem markets to co-ordinate landscape-scale public benefits from nature. *PLOS ONE* 17 (1), e0258334.
- Reed, M.S., Stevens, B., Jensen, E., Merrel, I., Grandemange, Y., O'Halloran, F., Frere-Scott, J., Glendinning, J., 2024a. Overcoming barriers to the engagement of supply-side actors in Scotland's peatland natural capital markets - Final Report. Scottish Government.
- Reed, M.S., Cadwaladr-Rimmer, I., Everett, R. (2024b). Community benefit options for natural capital markets in Scotland. Available online at: https://www.hutton.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/Community-Benefit-workshop-report_FINAL_21Aug.pdf.
- Reed, M.S., Jensen, E.A., Noles, S., Conneely, D., Kendall, H., Raley, M., Tarrant, A., Oakley, N., Hinson, C., Hoare, V., Marshall, K., 2025. Analyzing who is relevant to engage in environmental decision-making processes by interests, influence and impact: the 3i framework. *J. Environ. Manage.* 373, 123437.
- Rockström, J., Steffen, W., Noone, K., Persson, Å., Chapin III, F.S., Lambin, E., Lenton, T. M., Scheffer, M., Folke, C., Schellnhuber, H.J., Nykvist, B., 2009. Planetary boundaries: exploring the safe operating space for humanity. *Ecol. Soc.* 14 (2).
- SBTi, 2021. SBTi Corporate Net-Zero Standard Version 1.0. Available at: <https://sciencebasedtargets.org/resources/files/Net-Zero-Standard.pdf>.
- SBTi, 2022. Forest, Land and Agriculture (FLAG). Available at: <https://sciencebasedtargets.org/sectors/forest-land-and-agriculture>.
- SBTi, 2023. Beyond value chain mitigation. Available at: <https://sciencebasedtargets.org/beyond-value-chain-mitigation>.
- Schneider, L., La Hoz Theuer, S., 2019. Environmental integrity of international carbon market mechanisms under the Paris Agreement. *Clim. Pol.* 19 (3), 386–400.
- Scottish Forestry, 2022. Woodland Carbon Code Version 2.2. Available at: <https://woodlandcarboncode.org.uk/standard-and-guidance>.
- Scottish Government (2019). Scottish Government Good Practice Principles for Community Benefits from Onshore Renewable Energy Developments. Available at: https://consult.gov.scot/energy-and-climate-change-directorate/onshore-renewable-energy-developments/user_uploads/community-benefits-onshore-revised-gpp.pdf.
- Scottish Government, 2022a. Interim Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/interim-principles-for-responsible-investment-in-natural-capital/>.
- Scottish Government, 2022b. Land Reform in a Net Zero Nation. Available at: <https://consult.gov.scot/agriculture-and-rural-economy/land-reform-net-zero-scotland/>.
- Scottish Government, 2023. National Planning Framework 4. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/national-planning-framework-4/>.
- Scottish Government, 2024. Natural Capital Market Framework. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/natural-capital-market-framework/>.
- Scottish Land Commission, 2023. Community benefits from investment in natural capital: a discussion paper. Available at: https://www.landcommission.gov.scot/downloads/63eb8fd87d297_Community%20Benefit%20Discussion%20Paper.pdf.
- Sobkowiak, M., 2020. Rendering biodiversity calculable: a case study of UK biodiversity accounting and the construction of biodiversity indicators (Doctoral dissertation, University of Birmingham).
- Soil Association (2024) Investigating the feasibility for an Agroforestry Carbon Code - final report and recommendations. Available at: <https://www.soilassociation.org/farmers-growers/farming-news/2024/january/22/delivering-natural-capital-projects-alongside-food-production/#NEIRF>.
- Solman, H., Smits, M., van Vliet, B., Bush, S., 2021. Co-production in the wind energy sector: a systematic literature review of public engagement beyond invited stakeholder participation. *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* 72, 101876.
- Steffen, W., Richardson, K., Rockström, J., Cornell, S.E., Fetzer, I., Bennett, E.M., Biggs, R., Carpenter, S.R., De Vries, W., De Wit, C.A., Folke, C., 2015. Planetary boundaries: guiding human development on a changing planet. *Science* 347 (6223), 1259855.
- TCFD, 2023. Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures. Available at: <https://www.fsb-tcfd.org/>.
- Teytelboym, A., 2019. Natural capital market design. *Oxf. Rev. Econ. Policy* 35 (1), 138–161.
- TNFD, 2023. Task Force on Nature-related Financial Disclosures. Available at: <https://tnfd.global/>.
- van den Burg, S.W.K., Termeer, E.E.W., Skirtun, M., Poelman, M., Veraart, J.A., Selnes, T., 2022. Exploring mechanisms to pay for ecosystem services provided by mussels, oysters and seaweeds. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 54, 101407.
- VCMI, 2023. VCMI Claims Code of Conduct. Available at: <https://vcmintegrity.org/vcmi-claims-code-of-practice/>.
- Verra, 2023. VM0042 Methodology for Improved Agricultural Land Management, v2.0. Available at: <https://verra.org/methodologies/vm0042-methodology-for-improved-agricultural-land-management-v2-0/>.

WEF, 2020. Nature Risk Rising, Available online at https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_New_Nature_Economy_Report_2020.pdf.
Wunder, S., 2015. Revisiting the concept of payments for environmental services. *Ecol. Econ.* 117, 234–243.

Yu, H., Xie, W., Yang, L., Du, A., Almeida, C.M., Wang, Y., 2020. From payments for ecosystem services to eco-compensation: conceptual change or paradigm shift? *Sci. Total Environ.* 700, 134627.